

**THE PERSPECTIVE OF RESIDENTS IN THE TEACHER TRAINING
PROCESS: THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE PEDAGOGICAL
RESIDENCE PROGRAM IN THE TRAINING OF LITERACY
TEACHERS**

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ABSTRACT : This report deals with experiences with the Pedagogical Residency Program (RESPED), supported by the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), which is linked to the Ministry of Education (MEC), based on the subproject Literacy of the nucleus in Assú, of the State University of Rio Grande do Norte (UERN), The RESPED subproject, which is linked to the Ministry of Education (MEC), is based on the subproject Alfabetização (Literacy) of the Assú subproject of the University of the State of Rio Grande do Norte (UERN), and inserts undergraduate students of Pedagogy in the daily life of schools, bringing UERN closer to the basic school space, specifically the 1st and 2nd years of elementary school to participate in methodological and technological experiences and teaching practices that contribute to the literacy process of children from 5 to 7 years old. RESPED aims to induce the improvement of practical training in undergraduate courses, promoting the immersion of

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undergraduates in basic education schools. The experiences as residents took place at Complexo Educacional Doutor Pedro Amorim (CEPA), in a 2nd year class, in the second semester of 2020. The pedagogical practices were adapted to the remote model together with the teacher. The applied methodology includes in-depth observations, in the researched context, experience reports in the logbook of the experiences during the participation in the program. In short, the experiences in the classroom, such as observation, planning and regency, contributed to the construction of professional teaching practice, are real situations that demand the importance of dialogue between the theoretical and practical dimensions, reflection in the action of teachers being fundamental in the development of the formation of teacher identity that is built with the practices of everyday life from their values and knowledge.

Keywords: teacher. training. experiences. school. pedagogical residence.

INTRODUCTION

In this experience report, the bibliographical research method was used, having as theoretical subsidies, authors that base on the initial and continuous teacher formation, with a qualitative approach. The experiences in the classroom provided an incentive for higher-level teacher training to work in the area of literacy, relating theory and practice, as well as their relationships with the knowledge and practices built in the daily life of basic education in the municipality of Assú/RN. As teachers in training, to achieve and share knowledge and knowledge for the practice of teaching, through exchanges with the other, is to carry out training with effectiveness and learning, through dialogues with the experiences of the course, building in the daily life, in the condition of practical residents that reflect not only reading and writing, but also orality, involving sociocultural, environmental and inclusion relations.

The resident's pedagogical practice takes place in the Early Years (1st to 5th year) of Elementary School, promoting their insertion in the reality of the classroom, contributing to the quality of their initial training. This possibility of theoretical-practical training is supported by public notice n. 005/2020 - PROEG/UERN that disciplined the selection process of subprojects to compose the institutional project of UERN's RESPED, in line with CAPES public notice - RP n. 01/2020. The experiences represent part of what is being developed at the Pedro Amorim Educational Complex (CEPA) in the municipality of Assú/RN.

The Pedagogical Residency comprises activities such as moments of theoretical studies, in meetings organized by the mentoring professor, and mediation in the classroom with preceptors and residents, having occurred in a remote format due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Studies on literacy, literacy and literacy were sent at the meetings, in which resident advisors and preceptors analyze and discuss studies based on the National Literacy Plan (PNA), promoting the adequacy of the curricula and pedagogical proposals of the initial training

courses for basic education teachers to the guidelines of the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC).

REFLECTIONS AND UNDERSTANDINGS ABOUT TEACHING PRACTICES IN THE CLASSROOM

During the residency, we observed the teaching practice, participated in interaction activities, analysis and production of knowledge in the classroom and in meetings. In Zaballa's view (1994), teaching practice makes it possible for us to get to know the problems that challenge teaching practice in the classroom and school routine. Problems do not occur in theory, as practice differs from theory in the educational process, considering the context of the school and the students. In this sense, who can show us how we should work to obtain quality education, from a perspective beyond pedagogy, with reflections linked to action to resolve the best way to teach and learn in a pandemic context in basic education? Responding to this question Zaballa (1994) states that:

[...] the encounter with reality in the classroom, raises difficulties in the teacher-student-training-society relationship and the many interactions arising from the teaching-learning process, as the dynamics of a class is developed in an environment facing dilemmas, or more properly, amid problematic spaces (ZABALLA, 1994, p. 63).

In this way, learning demands from the teacher a foundation and theoretical knowledge so that he can innovate his teaching practice for the social context of the students. Considering the teacher's pedagogical practice in the classroom, spaces for reflection are built on his role as an educator in the formation of critical thinking, allowing a cognitive and autonomous development for the student who begins his school journey.

And it is in this context that the National Curriculum Guidelines for Basic Education (DCN), from 2001, when dealing with the need for teachers to know different age groups of children so that they can understand the specificities that they will require. Through the Pedagogical Residency, resident students pass through different classes and can come into contact with specific age situations. (BRASIL, 2001).

The experiences in the classroom not only broadened the vision as future teachers and students of the Pedagogy course at UERN, but also made it possible to weave relationships between practice and theoretical studies in the area of literacy and literacy, carried out in the meetings by the mentoring professor of the project, which contributes to our activities as residents.

When interacting with students in the classroom, we observed that the children are attentive to the residents, as well as always responding to feedback via the WhatsApp application. In this way, we can learn about teaching through applied classes, observing writing, orality, student performance, planning and dialogue with the preceptor about the lesson plans, and meetings at the pedagogical residency with the literacy and literacy project group. . In this sense, Nóvoa (2003), when reflecting on the experiences of students in the process of teacher training, states that:

It is clear that the University has an important role to play in teacher education. For reasons of prestige, scientific support, cultural production. But a teacher's essential baggage is acquired at school, through experience and reflection on experience. This reflection does not come out of nowhere, by a kind of spontaneous generation. It has its own rules and methods. (NÓVOA, 2003, p. 05).

It is from our relationships and experiences with the other that we build our teaching identity and, consequently, we develop ways to face and overcome the countless challenges that arise from the teaching and learning process. In this sense, both the university context and the basic school transmit knowledge and knowledge to residents that are crucial for teacher training, not only academically, but in social and personal life.

THE LEARNING PATH IN THE PEDAGOGICAL RESIDENCE PROGRAM

The observation activities began in module I of the RESPED Program, carried out with a workload of 86 hours, which includes studies, research of methodological contents and familiarity with students, preceptors and activities related to the project, in addition to investigation regarding the adaptation of the students the new routine.

In the remote teaching model, student interaction took place gradually; they adapted over time to remote classes, participating and interacting during class. The moments of analysis in the classes happened before the conducting phase. A priori, we sought to know the reality and characteristics of the school and the class, with that, the planning took place, where we prepared classes that met the needs and particularities of the class, thus ensuring significant results.

However, in order to obtain student learning, we had the participation of the preceptor at times and the help of the textbook, bringing the contents dynamically, through video classes, in a playful way so that the pedagogical work could happen together with the project successfully, as well as the interventions were made, re-signifying according to the context of the 2nd year class.

In addition, interdisciplinarity was worked on with a view to approaching the contents in an integrated manner, stimulating the discovery of children's pleasure in carrying out their tasks in disciplines such as Art, which encourages the development of aesthetic and ethical skills and competences.

In the Portuguese Language discipline, activities were applied to facilitate the practice of reading and writing, the construction of short texts, in addition to orality competence, developed in the literacy and literacy process, enabling the formation of more active subjects, through the various manifestations of the language.

As a result, the results of the classes developed were achieved, as the returns of activities were returned by the students with the family monitoring through the WhatsApp application, and the activities applied by the interaction and their relationship with the Literacy and Literacy project, as well as as well as the improvement of spelling, writing and orality, contributing to the entire educational development of students.

The school activities of the Doutor Pedro Amorim Educational Complex - CEPA, returned in a blended or hybrid way, on September 8, 2021, and we, as residents, applied classes remotely according to the planning articulated with the responsible preceptor, considering that UERN classes only return to their in- person calendar in 2022, shortly after students and employees have their complete vaccination schedule, in order to return to teaching in a more effective and successful way.

This process of teaching to read and write aggregated our social practices during and after the experiences of conducting in the Pedagogical Residence, building an important path in our teacher training, developing responsibility, sensitivity towards students, considering the social contexts of children from early years.

It is certainly in initial training that we experience reflections on pedagogical practices, didactics and their purposes for a significant result for our teacher identity in the face of the challenges of the reality of education.

Thus, considering the knowledge in the life of a teacher in this process of humanization, it can be said that “teacher training comprises an emancipatory project” (PIMENTA, 1999, p. 31). In this way, it is necessary that the teacher participates in the emancipatory processes of the school community, that he can provide meaning and meaning to teaching, which must be critical and conscious, and this involves a reflection in relation to the problems witnessed in his practice, being mediator in sharing knowledge and expertise in the classroom for the construction of citizenship.

Thus, scientific knowledge is essential to support our practices in teaching, innovating methods and agreeing with the reality of the school in initial and continuous training, valuing teacher training in relation to the practice of experiences during participation in the project, encouraging the student of the Pedagogy course to learn to be a teacher.

In this way, knowledge is woven with each new challenge, which is why we must be guided by the experience of the teaching knowledge of the program's preceptors and advisors, since there is a relationship between teaching and learning, theory and practice and, as undergraduates In progress, we aim for professional qualification in teacher training with autonomy and rationality to teach students with mastery about values, democracy, citizenship and the right to absolute freedom with critical reflection.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In view of the above, knowing and interacting with the class on a daily basis, such as being part of the students' training, is of great relevance for everyone's learning, whether they are preceptors, residents or students, because, in a unique way, each member of this web of learning and teaching contributed to our teacher training process, despite facing a pandemic context in which we used an atypical teaching model, which was challenging for everyone who is part of the school community, as well as dealing with technologies was innovative for everyone .

The conjunctures of the pedagogical praxis must proceed from a critical analysis based on the context of the school, the class and the children's perspective. It is also important to learn interactively, exploring knowledge from living in the classroom and in your social life with your family, colleagues, teachers and your books, whether they are didactic or not.

Therefore, the literacy practices worked in the classroom were successful in literacy, which lead us to conclude that literacy and literacy happen together, articulating with social practices that contribute to the acquisition of the ability to understand reading, inside and outside the classroom. school context. Therefore, it is necessary for the teacher to contextualize the contents to the student's reality, approaching them in order to be able to carry out learning in an inseparable way.

Our experiences in the classroom at the Doutor Pedro Amorim Educational Complex (CEPA), in partnership with the Advanced Campus of Assú, was an educational and formative process for our political, historical, social and cultural identities. The project encourages

residents to train teachers based on the theories studied on the university campus, putting them into practice in the classroom through the Literacy and Literacy subproject, at the Assú center.

Finally, the biggest lesson that remains is that we must look at ourselves as future teachers and that we can continually re-signify our teacher training to provide and contribute to a fair and quality Brazilian education.

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